

SOCIAL SCIENCES

GENERAL ISSUES ON THE PURIFICATION AND ENRICHMENT OF THE ALBANIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to highlight some historical and linguistic issues, which have influenced the purification and development of the Albanian language over the years. In the entirety of our social and cultural life, language development occupies a special place. This development is related to the establishment of norms in the entire system and subsystems of the literary language. Many researchers have made a valuable contribution, where with their studies in linguistics they have raised, enriched, sound foundations in the field of the Albanian language. In order to address the problems of the Albanian language, the historical, social and linguistic factors must be taken into account, in such a way that the phenomena that have occurred and the various problems can be understood as clearly as possible. The methodology used is the research methodology used by Albanian and foreign scholars.

Keywords: Albanian language, general lexicon, terminological lexicon

Introduction

E. Çabej³ wrote that "...language reflects a nationality, it is the clearest reflection of a nationality and its culture. The degree of richness and purity of the language is an indicator of the level of this culture...". Encouraged by these principles, authors such as Gjon Buzuku, Pjetër Bogdani, Pjetër Budi, Fran Bardhi have begun the work to purify and enrich the Albanian language, and in their writings we can find words⁴ like *derëtar*, *dëftues*, *grykësia*, *gjuhëtar*, *këshilltar*, *pushim rrëfim* etj.,; following it later, with their studies and contribution Xhuvani, Çabej, Demiraj, Kostallari etc.

The main purpose⁵ of the renaissance humanist was laying the foundations of the literary language, giving their contribution to the purification and enrichment of the Albanian language. E. Lafe write⁶: "...the request of the renaissance humanist for the purity of the language had a clear political content: we must remove from our language the foreign words that have taken the place of the beautiful Albanian words, ...". The renaissance humanist have used two ways to enrich and purify the language: 1) taking words from the popular discourse, raising them to a meaningful level, such as subject, stream, etc.; 2) formation of new words or neologisms⁷ like: *fletore*, *mësim*, *padije*, *shënim*, *shumicë thelloj*, *fushatë*, *jetëdhënës*, *ligjdhënës*, *ndërgjegje*, *pikë*, *theks*, *zanore*, *dëgjim*, *dritare*, *hapësirë*, *papunësi*, *lindje*, *perëndim*, *jugperëndim*, *veriperëndim*, *mesditë*, *kryeministër*, *qeverita*, *shumës*,

rrokje, *i shquar*, *i pashquar* etj. With the contribution of the renaissance humanist, the Albanian language took on the features and functions of a national literary language for the first time.

Results and discussion

After the declaration of independence, other linguists also followed this path, having a proper fund and direction for the enrichment and purification of the Albanian language. As mentioned, the Komisia Letrare e Shkodres (Literary Commission of Shkodra) and the Educational Congress of Lushnje, have played a significant role, which with the decisions taken encouraged the continuation of the work according to the principles of the renaissance. Many studies have been conducted in this direction.

Following the beforementioned principles, the studies of Xhuvani, Çabej, etc. played an important role in Albanian linguistics. Xhuvani devoted himself to the task of purifying the language from foreign words and enriching it with words from Albanian itself and wrote

He also followed two paths for the purification and enrichment of the language⁸: 1) the use of the right words that the people speak in the spoken language; 2) the study of the language of our old writers. Even Çabej has made a direct contribution to the development of the language, giving special importance to its purification and enrichment. With the same principles, he also looked for the Albanian word taken from the spoken

³ Çabej E., Për pastërtinë e gjuhës shqipe, Mësuesi 28 mars 1979

⁴ Çabej E., Për pastërtinë e gjuhës shqipe, Gjuha Jonë I, 1981 pp 38

⁵ Domi M., Probleme të sotme të gjuhës letrare dhe detyra të kulturës së gjuhës, Gjuha Jonë I, 1981, pp 26 - 34

⁶ Lafe E., Lufta për pastërtinë e gjuhës në kohën tonë, Studime mbi leksikon, III, 1989, pp 243

⁷ Çabej E., Për pastërtinë e gjuhës shqipe, Gjuha Jonë I, 1981 pp 39

⁸ Karapinjalli M., Aleksandër Xhuvani për pastërtinë e gjuhës shqipe, Studime për nder të Aleksandër Xhuvanit, 1986, pp 139 - 142

language⁹. Like Xhuvani, he also does not support excessive purism as he thinks that¹⁰ "...one of the main principles in replacing foreign words will be made with prudence. It should not be taken to extremes.... We should not proceed as in some languages where even international words and terms have been tried to necessarily replace them with elements of the country..."

In the post-Liberation period, the process of purification and enrichment was given a special place in studies and research work on the development of the language. We mention here the platform for the further purification and enrichment of the Albanian language¹¹ according to the Decision of the Council of Ministers¹² no 82 date. 7.4.1979 where it was proposed:

1. The creation of a permanent commission under the Council of Ministers for the organization of work for the further purification and enrichment of the Albanian literary language.

2. The commission has the following main tasks:

- To organize and direct the work for the purification and enrichment of our native language in all fields and to ensure that the results of research and studies in these fields are recognized by the general public and put into practice.

- To coordinate and control the work for the pronunciation and further unification of the technical-scientific terminology and for its implementation by all.

- To take care of the full implementation of the norm of the literary language in accordance with the tasks set by the decision of the Council of Ministers No. 50. Date 8.3.1974

- The Commission should design the platform that will serve as a basis for this action and a long-term work plan.

3. The Academy of Sciences, ministries and other research-scientific institutions, the University of Tirana and all the schools of our country should include the performance of the tasks that arise in this field in their annual plans and charge the most capable people for this. and more prepared.

4. In order to deal with the issues of cleaning and enriching the Albanian language, create the journal "Our Language" (Gjuha Jone), an organ of the Academy of Sciences.

Pursuant to the decisions of the Council of Ministers no. 50 dated 8.3.1974 and no. 82 dated 7.4.1974, the permanent Commission for the organization of work for the further purification and enrichment of the Albanian literary language, which was created by the Council of Ministers, has taken a number of measures to organize and direct the work for spelling and for the purification and enrichment of our native language in

all fields, as well as to recognize and implement the results of studies in these fields.

Under the influence of the economic-social and cultural-linguistic development, through a systematic and organized work, the process of cleaning and enriching the language has continued at a significant rate, gaining great skills and opportunities for expression. According to M.Domi¹³, the problems of language culture for further enrichment are addressed in several issues:

- everyone's acquisition and full application of literary language norms in all links of the language system

- the persistent and systematic fight against errors and violations of the norms and features of the Albanian language in general

- closely following the linguistic dynamics and attentive observation of its processes, occasional revision, based on the study, of the codification of the literary language, to complement and adapt it to the development of the language

- continuous enrichment of the literary language

- speeding up the processing of technical-scientific and political-social terminology

- preserving the originality and individuality of our language, cleaning it from unnecessary foreign elements

- raising the general language culture, in the first place with the continuous improvement of the teaching work of the school and with the powerful activity of mass information measures.

When we deal with the issue of the process for the purity of the language, we consider both the general lexicon and the terminological lexicon. Some criteria for language enrichment according to the beforementioned platform are¹⁴:

- The main way of enriching the lexicon is the formation of new words with word of the language itself and according to the production systems of the word-forming system of Albanian or with the way of pronouncing the component parts of foreign words, for example domosdoshmëri, krijimtari, mbishtresë, rastësi, dukuri, vetjak, vetëvendosje, përkim, parimor, etc.

- Another source of enrichment of the literary language is the wider use of words and phrases from the people's mouths, for example partice, grimcë, birëse, kah, pështjellë, gërryerje, mjedis, ngopje, endacak, tatëpjetë, etc.

- To enrich the lexicon of the literary language, words created in previous eras and which for various reasons have not come into use or have remained on the periphery of the language can be used, e.g. *trimëroj* (*inkurajoj*), *nismë*, *nismëtar*, *ngrehinë* etj.

⁹ **Leka F.** Prof Eqerem Cabej për pastërtinë e gjuhës shqipe dhe për pasurimin e leksikut dhe të terminologjisë, *Studime Filologjike*, 3, 1988, pp 87 - 92

¹⁰ **Çabej E.**, Për pastërtinë e gjuhës shqipe, *Gjuha Jonë I*, 1981, pp 44

¹¹ From the activity of the permanent commission for the organization of work for the further purification and enrichment of the Albanian literary language, journal *Our Language I*, 1981, pp. 13 - 17

¹² *Idem* pp 11-12

¹³ **Domë M.** Probleme të sotme të gjuhës letrare dhe detyra të kulturës së gjuhës, *Gjuha Jonë I*, 1981, pp 28

¹⁴ Some criteria for enriching the Albanian language and cleaning it from unnecessary foreign words, journal (*Gjuha Jone*) *Our Language I*, 1981, pp. 18 - 25

Some criteria for the purification of the language:

- The different layers of borrowed elements of the Albanian lexicon will be distinguished and the same attitude towards them will not be maintained

- The issue of replacing words of foreign origin that have entered the Albanian language for centuries and that are known and used by the entire people will not be raised.

- The issue of replacing international words or internationalisms, such as *revolucion*, *kushtetutë*, *komunizëm*, *planet*, *satelit*, *raketë*, *oqean*, *atom*, etc., will not be discussed. Words that are used

only in Romance languages (Italian, French, etc.) will not be called internationalisms. Efforts will be made to replace these words with Albanian words.

Some sources and main ways to clean up our language and phraseology:

- The richness of our words and phraseology will be widely used.

- New words will be created from Albanian's own dough. This includes neologisms, colloquial words.

- The work that was done for the pronunciation of foreign words during the renaissance and in the period of independence will be re-evaluated, in order to put into use the words that are well created and that respond to the needs of cleaning and enriching the language.

In this regard, the Albanian language has reached a high level of development. The unification of the language, the enrichment of the vocabulary with new formations through word-forming tools have influenced the development and the values that this language takes. Researcher V. Memisha emphasizes that "this development appears first, in the enrichment of the lexicon and it is a two-way process: horizontal enrichment, as enrichment of the lexical structure with new words and phraseological units; vertical (semantic) enrichment, as enrichment of the semantic structure with new meanings."¹⁵

This researcher claims that "Horizontal enrichment, in lexicology, is seen as enrichment of the lexical structure of the language, as a numerical addition of words. The main feature of this development of the lexicon nowadays is the tendency for symmetry and systematicity, this in all layers or paradigmatic groups. In the written discourse especially, but also in the spoken one, they are rapidly being put into use with thousands

of new units. One direction of the enrichment of the Albanian lexicon is the introduction into wide use of phraseology related to the material and spiritual world of our people, but also to the cultural and scientific world of fields developed in the international arena. Lexicography also helps. Academician J. Thomai, published in 1999 the phraseological dictionary of the Albanian language, with about 12,000 units¹⁶.

Conclusions

Today's literary language had its beginnings in the second half of the 19th century. The development of the Albanian language in the 19th century took off from the movement of the renaissance humanist, where a good part of them tried to write in pure Albanian. They began to purify and enrich it with words from the Albanian words themselves, drafting texts in various fields of scientific knowledge, literary works, other writings of a political-patriotic character. Under these conditions, some words of the popular language were given new meanings or new word strings were created that were missing from the Albanian vocabulary.

In the creation of new words, they were mainly based on the formation of linguistic calques where they used the tools of the Albanian language such as suffixes, prefixes, composites.

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¹⁵ V. Memisha, Rreth intelektualizimit të leksikut të shqipes, në Seminari II..., Tetovë, 2008, pp 194

¹⁶ J. Thomai, Fjalori frazeologjik i gjuhës shqipe, Tiranë, 2010